

Food Authenticity and its Importance for Customer Satisfaction in Terms of Persuasion

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Abstract:

The process of certifying food as halal, which involves identifying hidden ingredients, technological processing, manufacturing methods, and species substitution in halal food products, has become more popular due to rising public awareness of food safety and quality. This emphasizes how meticulous research into analytical methods is required to generate accurate and reliable data for monitoring and controlling the authenticity of halal food. This paper provides a succinct, unbiased overview of recent findings about the analytical techniques used to determine if food is truly halal.

Keywords: Food authentication; Consumption; Customer satisfaction; Food safety

1. Introduction:

Food authenticity is a major concern for the food industry as well as consumers for a variety of reasons, including legal compliance with religious beliefs, whether or not it is permitted, economic considerations (the right foods at the right price), and the assurance of a consistent, well-defined quality with the use of appropriate ingredients (no harmful substitutes) [1]. In general, pig derivatives are less expensive than cow or sheep derivatives. As a result, compounds of pork are utilized in many different dietary systems. In many nations, it is common practice to adulterate food and feed products by combining meats and fats from several less expensive sources and labeling them incorrectly or with ambiguous information. For some clients, misleading labeling, debasing with less expensive species, or disregarding strict specifications are big problems [2].

Globally, halal food consumption has increased recently, especially among Muslims. The halal food industry is growing rapidly and has a lot of promise. It is present in Asia, the Middle East,

Africa, Europe, and America. It is projected that the approximately 2 billion Muslims in the globe would spend US\$ 1400 billion on halal food by 2020; by 2050, this amount is estimated to have climbed by more than 10 times, reaching US\$ 15,000 billion. The Pew Research Center estimates that by 2030, there will be 2.2 billion Muslims globally, underscoring the importance of the halal and clean food sectors given that the GDPs of Muslim countries are expanding more quickly than those of Western countries [3, 4]. The 21st-century scientific and technological progress, particularly in the food processing sector, has led to the diversification of food components, including gelatin, genetically modified (GM) foods, and medicinal items, among Muslims [5, 6].

Customers, both Muslim and non-Muslim, who buy halal food items due to quality, environmental, and health concerns have broadened the market [7]. Only halal items that satisfy certain conditions are acceptable to Muslims. Products like alcohol and pork, which are strictly forbidden in Islam, are frequently combined with the most popular halal cuisines like chicken and beef. The consumption rate of halal beef and chicken in 2017 was 15.0% and 15.8%, respectively, based on the global consumption rate [8], as well as balanced ideal food sources [9]. Owing to the significance of the halal market, producers and consumers alike need to have a comprehensive grasp of how Islamic Syariah law—which establishes guidelines for Muslims to abide by based on the Holy Quran and Hadith—functions and is administered. Since halal food cannot be determined by taste, texture, or smell, it is difficult to verify.

Two techniques, called protein and DNA analysis, can be used to find and determine the presence of pig and its derivatives in food items. Nevertheless, because proteins are very sensitive and rapidly denatured by high temperatures during processing, the method for protein analysis is limited by these characteristics [10]. The DNA-based methods include conventional polymerase chain reaction (PCR), real-time PCR, PCR restricted fragment length polymorphism (PCR-RFLP), and species-specific PCR [11, 12]. Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) is the most effective technique for the very sensitive and precise identification of animal species and their derivatives in some highly processed food products [13], however, both proteins and nucleic acids are severely damaged in the finished food items. In addition, depending on the particular food category, gelatin or the majority of dietary items contain quite little amount DNA.

2. Foods that require for halal authentication: Certification for halal is necessary for all kinds of food, especially meat items. This is due to the fact that meat products constitute a significant portion and are necessary for human nutrition. As demand grows and prices rise, there is a greater likelihood of unlawful adulteration, substitution, and mislabeling of meat and meat products [14]. For consumers who have religious prohibitions against consuming pork, counterfeit meat products pose a severe risk due to their low cost [15]. In addition to meat, halal cuisine cannot contain alcohol. Alcohol is frequently employed in the creation of food or as a byproduct in the processing of food, especially ethyl alcohol, or ethanol. Moreover, Muslims must eat the flesh of animals that have been killed according to Islamic law and with the correct halal procedures. Industries employ a lot of porcine gelatin, and this product is considered haram and sold not just to Jews and Muslims but also to vegetarians and others who are allergic to swine products.

3. Methods used to test food authenticity: The examination of the authenticity of halal food in various food product categories is dealt with in the following sections using both conventional methods and state-of-the-art research. A decade ago, established methods such as electrophoresis and physicochemical approaches were used to examine halal food. Conventional techniques are inexpensive and simple to use, but they require tedious and time-consuming sample preparation procedures. Furthermore, it's challenging to interpret the results due to the absence of reliable datasets [16]. Molecular spectroscopy and high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), which produce validated and reliable results, are two techniques that must be used to check and verify the results. Furthermore, the Internet of Things (IoT), chemometrics, and artificial intelligence (AI) may be integrated with the state-of-the-art techniques previously discussed to enhance the accuracy, speed, and capability of multiplexed analyte detection.

4. Necessity of food authentication: Food authenticity not only guarantees food safety and quality, but it also helps producers and customers financially. Producers may safeguard their reputation and brand by authenticating items, and buyers can feel certain about the goods they are buying [17]. Food fraud has an effect that extends beyond monetary losses and reputational damage. Food goods that are tainted or incorrectly labeled can seriously endanger public health. Eating foods that aren't authentic can cause allergic responses, foodborne infections, and

chronic health problems. Verifying the legitimacy of food is an essential line of defense that lowers possible health risks and prevents dangerous items from reaching customers [18, 19]. Due to food adulteration, a number of sophisticated analytical methods have been assessed recently for their use in food authentication, particularly for halal food items. Panels of qualified human experts have evaluated the authenticity of halal food in the past, but this traditional method has a number of drawbacks, including drawn-out processes, expensive costs, and subjectivity [20]. Muslim customers are increasingly concerned about halal products, not just for food items but also for non-food items like medications and cosmetics. Cosmetic and pharmaceutical items might be contaminated with non-halal substances. The halal food controversy frequently touches on meat and other animal-based items. Customers must be informed of the ingredients in the food they consume, yet some producers purposefully mislead customers about the origin or quality of food items in order to profit. Additionally, as the need for food and commerce rises, there is a major risk of food adulteration and replacement.

Figure 1. Food Authenticity Testing Market Size (%) by Region

5. Biosensor in detection of food authenticity: Biosensor based calorimetric DNA detection process used in decade of nineties. A new era in food authentication platforms has begun with the application of biosensor technology in the detection of halal food. It is a portable analytical device that combines biological recognition components including enzymes, antibodies, DNA,

and entire cells with an appropriate transducer to convert biochemical recognition into electrical, optical, or any other sort of signal depending on the transducer employed [21]. This system uses biosensor a device made of specific enzyme or gene that utilizes chemical structure of particular subjected sample to identify its similarity with adulteration. The use of biosensors in the food business has drawn a lot of interest for determining indicators such food freshness, safety, and quality of various food items, particularly for the detection of non-halal components. They successfully created a hybrid nano-bioprobe (biosensor) to detect pig DNA, with a 15–30 nucleotide mitochondrial genome as the target DNA marker. For the investigation, a swine cytb gene's 27-nt A1UI-cut fragment was used [22]. Alcohol biosensors, as compared to spectrometric (short-wave near-infrared [SW-NIR] spectrometer) and chromatographic (GC/liquid chromatography) approaches, which demand pricey equipment and intricate sample pre-treatment, offer superior selectivity and specificity, claim Das and Goswami. Beverages and meat items are both analyzed using biosensors. This method is inexpensive, takes less time, and may be scaled down for on-site, real-time monitoring. Additionally, this method involves little sample preparation (such as simple dilution) and does not require human involvement. The stability of the biosensors in actual samples is a problem. According to a research by Kuswandi et al. (2014), the ethanol biosensor's stability was assessed every week since its reaction level maintained at 70% after 8 weeks after the first response [23]. Many research using the optical approach have been done to assess the quality of meat containing pig. It has also been developed to recognize deer, rabbit, duck, chicken, cow, horse, lamb, and pork using an optical thin film microarray approach on silicon-based surfaces, leading to optical biosensor chips.

6. PCR technique for identification: Polymerase chain reaction-restriction fragment length polymorphism (PCR-RFLP) is one type of old methods used for detection of pork in foods and meat [24]. The extremely sensitive PCR method may rapidly amplify DNA segments and produce billions of copies of DNA fragments Gene sequences may be found and identified utilizing visual methods based on size and load using the PCR method [24]. However, PCR has several disadvantages, such as the following: (1) The PCR procedure uses a DNA polymerase that is prone to errors and can yield fragments with mutations. (2) The specificity of the resulting PCR product may be altered if non-specific primers attach to other similar sequences in the template DNA. (3) A primer design usually required some preceding sequence

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in order to create PCR products. The DNA template, which can be single- or double-helix, two oligonucleotide primers that encircle the DNA sequence to be amplified, four nucleotide triphosphates, or dNTPs, heat-stable polymerization, and buffered magnesium ions all affect how well the PCR process goes. Three steps make up the PCR process: (1) denaturation, (2) adhesion, and (3) extension. The reaction is carried out by a rotation of temperature. High heat causes the DNA double helix to separate (melt). After that, the temperature is lowered to enable the primer to adhere to the template. The primer's melting temperature (T_m), which is 5 °C below the main T_m , also affects the temperature during the complement hybridization sequence. Adhesion is characterized by a drop in temperature (usually 45–60 °C) that allows the primer to attach to template strands. The primer and template may not come into contact due to ineffective adhesion temperature. Therefore, in order to maximize efficiency, temperature should be varied and ultimately set at around 72 °C, which is excellent for primer lengthening polymerization when dNTP is involved [25, 26].

7. Conclusion: The ability to recognize food fraud concerns and verify food authenticity has increased, which presents an opportunity for food marketing and branding. Synthetic food may be low-quality and perhaps harmful. Since they are of a higher caliber, real cooking items may cost more. Genuine foods shouldn't be as expensive as imitations.

Conflict of interest: Not declared.

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